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Abstract: Integrated power and desalination plants (IPDP) may provide a key solution for the pressing freshwater deficit and energy problems in many regions of the world. The current investigates the potential of low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) and thermal vapor compression multi-effect distillation (TVC-MED) coupled with a concentrating solar power (CSP) plant, taking also into account a reverse osmosis (RO) unit connected to the same power plant. The thermodynamic performance of the proposed schemes of IPDP has been evaluated by the assessment of the net output thermal capacity and the net power cycle efficiency of the different configurations, together with the estimation of the size of the solar field required to provide the corresponding thermal capacity. The results show that the combination with LT-MED is more efficient thermodynamically than with TVC-MED. Also, the CSP plant coupled with TVC-MED is more cost-effective than the independent processes because it requires a smaller solar field. The integration of a MED plant reduces the cooling requirements of a CSP power plant but the CSP+RO combination has a better thermodynamic efficiency. However, the difference with respect to CSP+LT-MED is small, so the latter can be more convenient in some cases.

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Editor
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Dear Editor,

Please consider the following paper for publication in Desalination journal.

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“Simulation and evaluation of the coupling of desalination units to parabolic-trough solar power plants.”

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Yours, sincerely

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Simulation and evaluation of the coupling of desalination units to parabolic-trough solar power plants

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Highlights

Simulations with a computational model show that the combination of concentrated solar power (CSP) plants with LT-MED desalination plants is more efficient thermodynamically than with TVC-MED.

The CSP plant coupled with TVC-MED is more cost-effective than the independent processes because it requires a smaller solar field.

The integration of a MED plant reduces the cooling requirements of a CSP power plant but the CSP+RO combination has better thermodynamic efficiency.

The difference with respect to CSP+LT-MED is small, so the latter can be more convenient in some cases.

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Abstract

Integrated power and desalination plants (IPDP) may provide a key solution for the pressing freshwater deficit and energy problems in many regions of the world. The current investigates the potential of low-temperature multi-effect distillation (LT-MED) and thermal vapor compression multi-effect distillation (TVC-MED) coupled with a concentrating solar power (CSP) plant, taking also into account a reverse osmosis (RO) unit connected to the same power plant. The thermodynamic performance of the proposed schemes of IPDP has been evaluated by the assessment of the net output thermal capacity and the net power cycle efficiency of the different configurations, together with the estimation of the size of the solar field required to provide the corresponding thermal capacity. The results show that the combination with LT-MED is more efficient thermodynamically than with TVC-MED. Also, the CSP plant coupled with TVC-MED is more cost-effective than the independent processes because it requires a smaller solar field. The integration of a MED plant reduces the cooling requirements of a CSP power plant but the CSP+RO combination has a better thermodynamic efficiency. However, the difference with respect to CSP+LT-MED is small, so the latter can be more convenient in some cases.

Keywords: Multi-effect distillation; reverse osmosis; solar desalination; cogeneration.

1. Introduction

Nowadays many regions of the world are suffering from water and energy problems but water scarcity will become critical during the first half of this century. Competition for water resources exists at all levels and is forecast to increase with demands for water supply in almost all countries. In 2030, 47% of world population will be living in areas of high water stress. More than 5 billion people (67% of the world population) may still be without access to adequate sanitation in 2030 [1]. Moreover, climatic change and climatic variability can have a dramatic impact on water supplies, the most obvious being drought [2].

At the same time, the expected future demand for energy in 2030 will be in the order of about 17 TW [3]. Clearly the traditional energy sources will be unable to satisfy that demand. In the next few decades, oil will cease to be the dominant resource, although it is not yet clear today which source of energy will replace it. There is no solution to any sustainable water and energy future without the strong participation of renewables in general and, in particular, solar energy, which has the highest potential of all renewable energies [4]. Therefore, technologies must be developed to use solar energy for solving future energy and water problems.

In the current context of concentrating solar power (CSP) technology development, CSP and water cogeneration (CSP+D) is a very attractive concept, as that combination could potentially solve power and water problems in many of the world's arid and semi-arid areas [5]. Moreover, power and water production in an integrated system is of interest for reducing the cost of solar generation by making better use of a common infrastructure and the economics of scale of the steam turbine [6].

Several different basic integrated power and desalination plants (IPDP) configurations are possible for generating electricity and producing fresh water from seawater [7]. In Gulf countries, most power plants are IPDP that integrate the three conventional (MSF, MED and RO) desalination technologies at different levels: (i) multi-stage flash (MSF) units operating with steam extracted from turbines, or supplied directly from boilers; (ii) multi-effect distillation (MED) units using steam extracted from a turbine or supplied directly from boilers and; (iii) reverse osmosis (RO) systems supplied with electricity from a steam power plant or from a combined gas/steam power cycle. The preference of one scheme over another depends on many factors, such as the required power to water ratio, cost of fuel energy charged to the desalting process, electricity sales, capital costs, and local requirements [8].

Different cogeneration plants reviews have been published. Kronenberg and Lokiec [9] described cogeneration with low-temperature MED (LT-MED) desalination plants. Yang and Shen [10] presented an energy cost analysis to produce water from an integrated power plant into LT-MED and thermal vapor compression MED (TVC-MED) units. Kamal [11] evaluated the benefits of integrating RO units with

1 existing power/desalination plants in the Middle East. In addition, some authors have made thermo-economic
2 analysis of cogeneration plants [12,13].

3 Focusing more on the coupling issue, different configurations for combined electricity and fresh water
4 production by an IPDP in the Middle East and North Africa have been proposed [14]. The desalination
5 systems used were RO, MED and a combination of both. Also, a thermal and environmental analysis for two
6 CSP+D schemes has been published [15]. The first configuration consisted of a CSP plant where parabolic-
7 trough solar collectors were used, coupled with a RO/LT-MED hybrid system. The second one is the same
8 but integrating a gas turbine unit with the solar power plant. The results showed that of the proposed schemes
9 the latter seemed the most effective in terms of technical, economic and environmental sustainability.

10 Regarding computer models, the basic features of the simulation by the software IPSEpro of small-scale
11 decentralized water and power cogeneration systems with hybrid renewable and fossil power have been
12 described [16].

13 This paper presents a thermodynamic analysis of different configurations for the combination of
14 desalination plants with CSP plants. The first three cases consider different concepts of MED plants (low-
15 temperature MED and thermal vapour compression MED) combined with a CSP plant. The fourth
16 configuration consists of a RO plant connected to the same power plant considered in the previous cases. In
17 all cases the freshwater production considered is the same. The thermodynamic analysis comprises
18 simulations of the integrated power and desalination facility and of the solar field required in each
19 configuration.

20 21 **2. Methodology**

22
23 The CSP plant consists of a large field of single-axis parabolic-trough solar collectors (LS3 type) aligned
24 on a north-south orientation and a thermal storage tank to provide additional operation when solar radiation is
25 not available. The collectors track the sun from east to west during the day to ensure it is continuously
26 focused on the linear receiver. The net power of the CSP plant has been considered in all configurations to be
27 50 MWe, which is the normal size of a commercial parabolic trough CSP plant [17]. The power cycle is
28 based on the Reheat Rankine cycle. The same operation parameters as in an existing commercial plant, SEGS
29 IX [18], have been selected with the only difference of the inclusion of a thermal storage. The system
30 operates with oil that is heated as it circulates through the absorber tubes of the solar collectors. Solar energy
31 is thus turned into thermal energy in the form of sensible heat of the oil, and stored within the thermal storage
32 tank. The inlet and outlet oil temperatures in the field are 295°C and 390°C, respectively.

33 The size of the desalination plant has been chosen based on a MED commercial plant supplied in 2005
34 by IDE Technologies Ltd. (Israel) to Reliance Industries Ltd. (India). The plant has a production of 14400
35 m³/day and 24-h operation have been considered.

36 The integration of MED facilities into CSP plants allow to reduce or replace the conventional cooling
37 unit of the steam cycle compared to the case of a conventional CSP plant connected to a RO system. MED
38 plants can operate at low-temperature (LT-MED) or with an increased efficiency by using thermal vapour
39 compression driven by high temperature steam (TVC-MED). The TVC-MED can be combined with the CSP
40 plant by using high temperature steam extracted from the turbine or directly from the steam obtained from
41 the solar field (thus decoupled from the power cycle). Therefore, the proposed configurations for this study
42 are:

- 43
- 44 • LT-MED unit coupled with the CSP plant (configuration 1).
- 45 • TVC-MED unit coupled with the CSP plant (configuration 2).
- 46 • Independent TVC-MED and CSP plant (configuration 3).
- 47 • RO unit connected to the CSP plant (configuration 4).
- 48

49 *2.1. Configuration 1*

50
51 A process flow diagram for this configuration is shown in Fig. 1. The thermal energy from the solar field
52 is exploited by a power conversion system consisting of a pre-heater, an evaporator and a superheater. The
53 resulting steam at a temperature of 371°C and a pressure of 104 bars is sent to a high pressure (HP) turbine
54 where after suffering an expansion process is extracted at a pressure of 17 bars in order to reheat it. The
55 reheated steam is routed to a low-pressure (LP) turbine at 371°C and 17 bars. In this turbine an intermediate
56 extraction of steam at 70°C takes place to feed a LT-MED plant after a further reheating process to obtain
57 saturated steam without increasing the temperature. The remaining steam in the turbine expands to 50°C,
58 producing power. Then, it is condensed in a conventional condenser and mixed with the saturated liquid
59 stream from the first effect of the LT-MED unit. The mixture is pumped back into the power conversion
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1 system.

2 3 2.2. Configuration 2

4
5 In Fig. 2 a process flow diagram is shown for this configuration. Steam is produced from the solar field
6 thermal energy at the same pressure and temperature as in the previous case. As before, steam expands
7 through a HP turbine to a pressure of 17 bars. However, a small fraction of this steam is now used as live
8 steam in a steam ejector after reheating to achieve saturation conditions. The remaining part of the extracted
9 steam is reheated to enter a LP turbine at 371°C and 17 bars, where it expands to 50°C producing power. In
10 the steam ejector, the live steam is mixed with saturated vapor extracted from an intermediate effect of the
11 TVC-MED plant at a temperature of 50°C. The resulting compressed vapor from the ejector is injected into
12 the first effect of the TVC-MED plant at 70°C to feed the thermal distillation process. Finally, the saturated
13 liquid from the condenser is mixed with the saturated liquid from the TVC-MED unit and the mixture is
14 pumped into the power conversion system.

15 16 2.3. Configuration 3

17
18 This configuration (see process flow diagram in Fig. 3) is similar to the previous one but with the
19 difference that the TVC-MED unit is decoupled from the power cycle. This means that the steam ejector is
20 driven by live steam produced from the solar field thermal energy in an additional power conversion system
21 (at 204.3°C and 17 bars) instead of extracted from the turbine. The rest of the process is the same as in the
22 previous configuration.

23 24 2.4. Configuration 4

25
26 A process flow diagram for this configuration is shown in Fig. 4. In this layout, as in previous
27 configurations, the power is generated by the same process as in a conventional CSP plant. However, in this
28 configuration the electrical output is maximized because there are not extractions which penalize the power
29 production. The RO plant is driven by the power output from the CSP plant.

30 31 2.5. Simulations

32
33 The thermodynamic analysis of the four different configurations has been carried out by the assessment
34 of the net output thermal capacity (which is the thermal power to be provided by the solar field) and the net
35 power cycle efficiency. This assessment has been performed by a computer model developed with
36 Engineering Equation Solver (EES). A set of nonlinear, algebraic equations is generated to characterize the
37 thermodynamic cycle in each case. All the components associated with the power cycle (pump, reheater, heat
38 exchanger, condenser and turbine) are analyzed by steady-flow energy equations.

39
40 In the turbines and pumps, actual expansion and compression processes, respectively, have been
41 considered. An isentropic efficiency of 85% has been considered for all. The actual steam enthalpy at the
42 outlet of the high pressure and low pressure turbines of all the configurations proposed has been calculated
43 through:

$$44 \quad \eta_{st} = \frac{h_{inlet} - h_{outlet}}{h_{inlet} - h_{outlet,i}} \quad (1)$$

45
46 where η_{st} is the isentropic efficiency, h_{inlet} is the enthalpy of the steam which enters the turbine, h_{outlet} is the
47 actual enthalpy at the outlet of the turbine and $h_{outlet,i}$ is the ideal enthalpy of the steam which leaves the
48 turbine. In configuration 1, the enthalpy of the extracted steam has been calculated with the assumption of
49 linear condition line of h - s between the inlet and the outlet of the turbine:

$$50 \quad \frac{h_m - h_{outlet}}{h_{inlet} - h_{outlet}} = \frac{s_m - s_{outlet}}{s_{inlet} - s_{outlet}} \quad (2)$$

51
52 where h_m and s_m are the enthalpy and the entropy at the point where the steam extraction has been done.

53
54 To calculate the steam ejector flow rates (both live steam and entrained vapor flow rates) a semi-
55 empirical model [19] has been considered assessing the entrainment ratio, which is defined as the ratio of the
56 flow rates of the motive steam q_{ms} and the entrained vapor q_e :

$$Ra = \frac{q_{ms}}{q_e} \quad (3)$$

The steam flow rate needed by the MED desalination plants has been calculated by:

$$q_{steam} = \frac{FWF \times \rho}{GOR} \quad (4)$$

where FWF is the fresh water production in m^3/day , ρ is the fresh water density in kg/m^3 (at $35^\circ C$ and 1 bar) and GOR is Gained Output Ratio, which is defined as the mass ratio between the distillate produced and the steam supplied to the system. A fresh water production of $14400 m^3/day$ has been taken into account. The GOR has been assumed to be 9.8 in LT-MED and 11.8 in TVC-MED [20].

Once the cycle is simulated, the evaluation of the thermodynamic efficiency of the cycle has been done by analysing the net power cycle efficiency, which can be calculated as follows:

$$\eta_{cycle} = \frac{P_{net,cycle}}{NOTC} \quad (5)$$

where $NOTC$ is the net output thermal capacity and $P_{net,cycle}$ is the net power cycle production.

The net output thermal capacity is given by:

$$NOTC = P_{pcs} + P_{RH} \quad (6)$$

where P_{pcs} and P_{RH} are the power required by the power conversion system and the reheaters of the cycle, respectively.

The net power cycle production is calculated as the gross turbine output (P_{turb}) minus the power required by the pumps (P_{pumps}):

$$P_{net,cycle} = P_{turb} - P_{pumps} \quad (7)$$

In all case studies, the analysis has been carried out considering a net power production of the plant (P_{net}) of 50 MW. The net power production of the plant is the net power production of the cycle minus the power required by the desalination plant (P_{desal}):

$$P_{net} = P_{turb} - P_{pumps} - P_{desal} \quad (8)$$

For the calculation of the power required by the desalination plant, a specific electric consumption of $1.5 kWh/m^3$ has been assumed in the case of the MED plant and $4 kWh/m^3$ in the case of RO [21].

Finally, considering the net output thermal capacity calculated before, the solar field size has been determined by a computer model developed in MATLAB. The parabolic trough solar field is based on the LS-3 type collector. A model is used for this collector based on the equations given in Appendix A [22-24]. The following parameters and assumptions have been taken into account in the simulations:

- North-South orientation.
- Plant location: Longitude $1.7899^\circ W$; Latitude $37.1006^\circ N$.
- Design point in the middle of June.
- Thermal storage capacity for 24-h solar operation at design day (fossil backup when the solar radiation is not available).
- The net output thermal capacity calculated before.
- Inlet temperature to the field: $295^\circ C$.
- Outlet temperature from the field: $390^\circ C$.

The simulations were carried out for Palomares, in the province of Almería in SE Spain. With about $1990 kWh/m^2 \cdot yr$ DNI radiation, this site represents a good location for CSP plants in the Mediterranean area. Radiation and ambient temperature data have been taken from a meteorological year type data set generated with the software PVSYST V4.35 (monthly horizontal global irradiance data, room temperature and wind velocity obtained with the Meteororm software [25]). The oil type is Monsanto VP-1 (its properties are determined using Monsanto software).

3. Results

The results obtained from the simulation of each configuration are shown in the corresponding process flow diagrams (Figs.1-4). In each figure, values of the state points of the thermodynamic cycle (temperature, pressure, enthalpy and entropy) and the resulting steam flow rates of each component of the cycle are shown. In the first configuration (Fig.1), the HP turbine requires 49.18 kg/s of steam, 16.91 kg/s are extracted from the LP turbine to feed the MED plant, so only 32.28 kg/s have to be condensed in the condenser. In configuration 2 (Fig.2) more steam is generated and used in the HP turbine (57.51 kg/s), but since 14 kg/s are used as live steam in the ejector, only 43.47 kg/s enter the LP turbine and are later sent to the condenser. In configurations 3 and 4 all the steam produced through the power conversion system of the power cycle must be condensed, since no extraction is done in the turbine. In the latter case, the flow of steam is slightly higher than in the former, since more power needs to be produced in the turbine for obtaining the same net power production while taking into account the consumption of the RO plant.

Table 1 presents a summary of the net output thermal capacity values obtained for each configuration and the required solar field design. It also shows the net efficiency of the power cycle for each case and the steam mass flow rate that is taken to the condenser of the power cycle. On one hand, it can be observed from the comparison between the three configurations involving MED units that option 1 (LT-MED coupled with the CSP plant) has the highest net power cycle efficiency of the three, because it requires the lowest net output thermal capacity to be provided by the solar field and therefore the smallest solar field. The coupling of a TVC-MED with a CSP plant (configuration 2) leads to a reduction of the net output thermal capacity with respect to a system composed of two independent plants (configuration 3), roughly a 3% decrease in the aperture area.

On the other hand, the largest net power cycle efficiency corresponds to option 4, which is the RO system connected to a CSP plant. This is explained by the extraction of steam from the turbine in configurations 1 and 2, which penalizes the power production. This decrease of efficiency is smaller in configuration 1, since the steam extracted from the turbine has a lower exergy. In the case of configuration 3, the additional solar power required for generating steam for the TVC penalizes even more the net power cycle efficiency. However, it can be observed that in both cases which integrate MED systems in a CSP plant (configurations 1 and 2) the power plant cooling requirements are lower, especially in configuration with LT-MED (about 40% less than in the CSP+RO case).

4. Conclusions

Simple simulations have been developed for different configurations of associating MED and RO desalination units with solar power plants composed of parabolic-trough collectors, in order to characterize the thermodynamic cycle and determine the solar field size needed to produce 14400 m³/day fresh water and 50 MW_e power.

The combination of a RO and a CSP plant has a better cycle efficiency than the layouts with MED units, although it involves more energy losses to the ambient during the cooling process of the power cycle. Moreover, the difference is not too large (less than 2% with respect to the best combination with MED). RO desalination has higher technical requirements than MED, which does not require sophisticated pretreatment of seawater and therefore needs less maintenance. Furthermore, in many regions of the world, such as the Persian Gulf, the seawater properties are not optimal for the use of RO as desalination process. Therefore, the combination of a MED plant with a CSP plant cannot be completely ruled out.

The integration of a TVC-MED plant into a CSP plant is more competitive than both plants independently. The coupling is more efficient thermodynamically than the decoupling, and also more economic since it requires a smaller solar field for the same power and water production.

The integration of a LT-MED plant into a CSP plant is more efficient from a thermodynamic and economic point of view than the integration of a TVC-MED. However, for the TVC-MED the GOR is higher since less thermal energy is required for the same freshwater production (part of the steam generated in one of the effects of the MED plant is recovered). In addition, the capital cost of the TVC-MED is lower, as steam is extracted from an MED effect as entrained vapour to the ejector and therefore the condenser of the desalination plant is smaller or can even be removed in the case that saturated steam is extracted from the last effect. Therefore, TVC-MED could be an alternative for the integration with CSP plants if further configurations are designed to minimize the decrease in the thermodynamic efficiency of the power cycle.

Appendix A

The solar field is based on the parabolic trough LS-3 type collector (see Table 2). In order to carry out

1 the simulations of the parabolic trough collectors solar field, which provide the number of collectors per row,
 2 the number of rows and finally the aperture area, the following equations have been used to develop the
 3 computer model.

4 The thermal power supplied by a LS3 collector taking into account the set design conditions is given by:

$$5 \quad P_{Q,collector \rightarrow fluid} = A_c \cdot I \cdot \cos(\varphi) \cdot \eta_{opt,0^\circ} \cdot K \cdot F_e - P_{Q,collector \rightarrow environment}$$

6 where I (W/m^2) is the direct solar radiation; φ the incidence angle; F_e the fouling factor, taken as 0.95 for the
 7 LS3 collector; and K the incidence angle modifier, given by the following expression [24]:

$$8 \quad K(\varphi) = 1 - 2.23073 \cdot 10^{-4} \varphi - 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \varphi^2 + 3.18596 \cdot 10^{-6} \varphi^3 - 4.85509 \cdot 10^{-8} \varphi^4 \quad 0^\circ < \varphi < 80^\circ$$

$$9 \quad K(\varphi) = 0 \quad 85^\circ < \varphi < 90^\circ$$

10 The thermal power is used to increase the enthalpy of the thermal oil (Δh):

$$11 \quad P_{Q,collector \rightarrow fluid} = q_m \cdot (h_{out} - h_{in}) = q_m \cdot \Delta h$$

12 where q_m (kg/s) is the oil mass flow rate in the collectors.

13 The increase of enthalpy can be calculated as a function of the specific heat of the oil ($C_p(T)$):

$$14 \quad \Delta h = \int_{T_{in}}^{T_{out}} C_p(T) \cdot dT$$

15 Integrating the previous equation between the oil inlet and outlet temperature collector (T_{in} , T_{out}), the
 16 following result is obtained:

$$17 \quad \Delta h = a \cdot (T_{out} - T_{in}) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot b \cdot (T_{out}^2 - T_{in}^2)$$

18 where the parameters have the constant values $a=1.479$ and $b=0.0028$.

19 The thermal losses of the collector to the environment are calculated as follows:

$$20 \quad P_{Q,collector \rightarrow environment} = U_L \cdot A_{abs} \cdot (T_{abs} - T_{room})$$

21 where the global heat loss coefficient U_L ($W/(m^2 \cdot ^\circ C)$) is given by:

$$22 \quad U_L = c + d \cdot (T_{abs} - T_{room}) + e \cdot (T_{abs} - T_{room})^2$$

23 being A_{abs} (m^2) the absorber tube area, T_{abs} the absorber temperature ($^\circ C$); T_{room} the room temperature ($^\circ C$)
 24 and the constants $c=2.8954$, $d=-0.0164$ and $e=0.000065$.

25 The oil mass flow rate in the collectors (q_m) is given by:

$$26 \quad q_m = V \cdot S$$

27 where S (m^2) is the transversal section of the absorber tube and V (m/s) the oil velocity inside the absorber
 28 tube, calculated by choosing a Reynolds number which guarantees a great heat transfer inside the absorber
 29 tube in the regime of turbulent flow. For the LS3 collectors, $Re=3 \times 10^5$ is considered, so that V can be
 30 assessed from the expression:

$$31 \quad Re = \frac{V \cdot ID \cdot \rho_o}{\mu_o}$$

32 where ρ_o (kg/m^3) is the oil density and μ_o ($kg/m \cdot s$) the oil dynamic viscosity, determined by the Monsanto
 33 software taking a mean temperature between the oil inlet and outlet temperature in the solar field.

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Nomenclature

A_{abs}	absorber tube area (m ²)
A_c	aperture area (m ²)
C_p	specific heat capacity (kJ/kg°C)
D	absorber diameter (m)
F_e	fouling factor
FWF	fresh water flow rate (m ³ /day)
GOR	Gain Output Ratio
h_{inlet}	enthalpy of the steam which enters the turbine (kJ/kg)
h_m	enthalpy at the point where the steam extraction is done (kJ/kg)
h_{outlet}	actual enthalpy at the outlet of the turbine (kJ/kg)
$h_{outlet,i}$	ideal enthalpy of the steam which leaves the turbine (kJ/kg)
I	direct solar radiation (W/m ²)
ID	inside diameter (m)
K	incidence angle modifier
L	longitude of the absorber (m)
$NOTC$	net output thermal capacity (MW)
P_{net}	net power production (MW)
$P_{net,cycle}$	net power cycle production (MW)
q_e	entrained vapor flow rate (kg/s)
q_m	oil mass flow rate (kg/s)
q_{ms}	motive steam flow rate (kg/s)
q_{steam}	feeding steam flow rate to the desalination plant (kg/s)
Re	Reynolds number
S	transversal section of the absorber tube (m ²)
s_m	entropy at the point where the steam extraction is done (kJ/kg°C)
T_{abs}	absorber temperature (°C)
T_{in}	oil inlet temperature collector (°C)
T_{room}	room temperature (°C)
T_{out}	oil outlet temperature collector (°C)
U_L	global heat loss coefficient (W/(m ² ·°C))
V	oil rate inside the absorber tube (m/s)
ρ	fresh water density (kg/m ³)
ρ_o	oil density (kg/m ³)
μ_o	oil dynamic viscosity (kg/m·s)
η_{st}	isentropic efficiency of the turbine
$\eta_{opt,0^\circ}$	optical peak efficiency
φ	incidence angle

References

- [1] The OECD Environmental Outlook to 2030, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Paris, France, 2008.
- [2] Energy Demands on Water Resources: Report to Congress on the Interdependency of Energy & Water, U.S. Department of Energy, Washington, DC, USA, 2006.
- [3] Renewables in Global Energy Supply. An IEA Fact Sheet, IEA Publications, Paris, France, 2007.
- [4] Webber, M.E., Catch-22: Water vs. Energy, Scientific American 18 (2008) 34-41.
- [5] Blanco, J., Alarcón, D., Zaragoza, G., Guillén, E., Palenzuela, P. and Ibarra, M., Expanding CSP research frontier: Challenges to be addressed by Combined Solar Power and Desalination plants, Proc. of the 16th SolarPaces Symposium, The CSP conference: Electricity, Fuels and Clean Water from concentrated solar energy, September, 21-24, 2010, Perpignan, France.
- [6] Blanco, J., Malato, S., Fernández-Ibañez, P., Alarcón, D., Gernjak, W., and Maldonado, M.I., Review of feasible solar energy applications to water processes, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 13 (2009) 1437-1445.
- [7] Darwish, M.A., Desalting fuel energy cost in Kuwait in view of \$75/barrel oil price, Desalination 208 (2007) 306-320.
- [8] Mussati, S., Aguirre, P. and Scenna, N.J., Dual-purpose desalination plants. Part II. Optimal configuration, Desalination 153 (2003) 185-189.

- 1 [9] Kronenberg, G. and Lokiec, F., Low-temperature distillation processes in single- and dual-purpose
2 plants, *Desalination* 136 (2001) 189-197.
- 3 [10] Yang, L. and Shen, S., Assessment of energy requirement for water production at dual-purpose plants in
4 China, *Desalination* 205 (2007) 214-223.
- 5 [11] Kamal, I., Integration of seawater desalination with power generation. *Desalination* 180 (2005), 217-
6 229.
- 7 [12] Bouzayani, N., Galanis, N. and Orfi, J., Thermodynamic analysis of combined electric power generation
8 and water desalination plants, *Applied Thermal Engineering* 29 (2009) 624-633.
- 9 [13] Uche, J., Serra, L. and Valeron, A., Thermo-economic optimization of a dual-purpose power and
10 desalination plant, *Desalination* 136 (2001) 147-158.
- 11 [14] Trieb, F. and Müller-Steinhagen, H., Concentrating solar power for seawater desalination in the Middle
12 East and North Africa, *Desalination* 220 (2008) 165-183.
- 13 [15] Alrobaei, H., Novel integrated gas turbine solar cogeneration power plant, *Desalination* 220 (2008) 574-
14 587.
- 15 [16] Perz, E.W. and Bergmann, S., A simulation environment for the techno-economic performance
16 prediction of water and power cogeneration systems using renewable and fossil energy sources,
17 *Desalination* 203 (2007) 337-345.
- 18 [17] Geyer, M., Hermann, A., Sevilla, J.A., Nebrera, A. and Zamora, G., Dispatchable solar electricity for
19 summerly Peak loads from the solar thermal projects Andasol-1 & Andasol-2, Proc. of the 13th
20 SolarPACES Symposium, 2006, Sevilla, Spain.
- 21 [18] Lotker, M., Barriers to Commercialization of Large Scale Solar Electricity. Lessons Learned from the
22 LUZ experience, Technical report published by Sandia National Laboratories, Albuquerque, NM, USA,
23 1991.
- 24 [19] El-Dessouky, H. and Ettouney, H., *Fundamentals of Salt Water Desalination*, 1st Edition, Elsevier
25 Science B.V, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 2002.
- 26 [20] Ophir, A. and Gendel, A., Steam driven large multi effect MVC (SD MVC) desalination process for
27 lower energy consumption and desalination costs, *Desalination* 205 (2007) 224-230.
- 28 [21] Trieb, F., Concentrating solar power for seawater desalination, Aqua-CSP Study report, German
29 Aerospace Center, Stuttgart, Germany, 2007.
- 30 [22] Zarza, E., Generación directa de vapor con colectores solares cilindro parabólicos, Technical Report of
31 Direct Solar Steam (DISS) Project, CIEMAT, Madrid, Spain, 2004.
- 32 [23] Incropera, F.P., Dewitt, D.P., Bergman, T.L. and Lavine, A.S., *Fundamentals of Heat and Mass*
33 *Transfer*, 6th Edition, Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA, 1996.
- 34 [24] González, L., Zarza, E. and Yebra, L.J., Determinación del Modificador por Ángulo de Incidencia de un
35 colector solar LS-3, incluyendo las pérdidas geométricas por final de colector, Project DISS Technical
36 Report DISS-SC-SF-30, Almería, Spain, 2001.
- 37 [25] Meteostest, 2003. *Meteonorm* documentation software version 5.102. <<http://www.meteonorm.com>>.
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Figures

Fig. 1. Diagram of configuration 1: LT-MED coupled with a CSP plant

Fig. 2. Diagram of configuration 2: TVC-MED coupled with a CSP plant

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Fig. 3. Diagram of configuration 3: independent TVC-MED plant and CSP plant

Fig. 4. Diagram of configuration 4: RO connected to a CSP plant

1 **Tables**

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4 **Table 1.**

5 Net output thermal capacity, number of rows, number of collectors, aperture area required for the field and
6 net power cycle efficiency resulting from each proposed configuration.

7

8 Configuration	9 Net output thermal capacity (MW _{th})	10 Number of rows	11 Number of collectors	12 Aperture area of the solar field (m ²)	13 Net power cycle efficiency (%)	14 Steam mass flow rate through the condenser (kg/s)
15 1	162	537	1074	585330	31.50	32.3
17 2	182	606	1212	660540	28.0	43.5
18 3	188	626	1252	682340	26.61	46.6
19 4	160	532	1064	579880	32.73	48.8

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24 **Table 2.**

25 Dimensions and characteristics of the parabolic trough LS-3 type collector.

26

27 Item	28 Value
29 A_c : aperture area	545 m ²
30 L : longitude of the absorber	99 m
31 D : diameter of the absorber	70 mm
32 ID : inside diameter of the absorber	65 mm
33 $\eta_{opt,0^\circ}$: optical peak efficiency	0.75

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Table 1.

Net output thermal capacity, number of rows, number of collectors, aperture area required for the field and net power cycle efficiency resulting from each proposed configuration.

Configuration	Net output thermal capacity (MW_{th})	Number of rows	Number of collectors	Aperture area of the solar field (m^2)	Net power cycle efficiency (%)	Steam mass flow rate through the condenser (kg/s)
1	162	537	1074	585330	31.50	32.3
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Table 2.

Dimensions and characteristics of the parabolic trough LS-3 type collector.

Item	Value
A_c : aperture area	545 m ²
L : longitude of the absorber	99 m
D : diameter of the absorber	70 mm
ID : inside diameter of the absorber	65 mm
$\eta_{opt,0^\circ}$: optical peak efficiency	0.75

Figure

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Figure 2

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Figure 3
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Figure 4
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